

Coconut tree disease segmentation using YOLOv8 (You Only Look Once version 8)

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ABSTRACT

The occurrence of plant diseases has a negative impact on agricultural production. If plant diseases are not observed in time, it will lead huge lose for farmers. Early detection is the basis for effective prevention and control of plant diseases, and they play a vital role in the management and decision making of agricultural production. Coconut palms are affected by a number of diseases, some of which are dangerous and the disease gradually reduces the strength of the palm causing severe loss in the yield. Coconut trees are also attacked by a number of fungi, bacteria, viruses and nematodes leading to significant quantitative and qualitative loss. In this paper, YOLO v8 algorithm combines both detection and segmentation tasks within a single, unified model, thus facilitating more accurate and granular recognition.

Key words: Segmentation, image processing, YOLO v8 and Disease.

INTRODUCTION

Image processing is a method to convert an image into digital form and perform some operations on it, in order to get an enhanced image or to extract some useful information from it. Image pre-processing techniques are used to improve the quality of an image before processing into an application [1]. This uses a small neighborhood of a pixel in an input image to get a new brightness value in the output image. These pre-processing techniques are also called filtration and resolution enhancement. Most of the imaging techniques are degraded by noise. In order to preserve the edges and contour information of the Agricultural plant images, the efficient denoising and an improved enhancement technique is required. Gaussian, Median and Wiener filters are used for image de-noising.

Image segmentation is a daunting task in automatic image processing analysis [2]. It occupies vital position in many image processing applications, and it consists of sub-dividing the image into its constituent parts. Also, it extracts the Region of Interest (ROI) that should be homogeneous as for a few attributes. Image segmentation algorithms are developed based on two basic properties of intensity values: a)Similarity –Based b)Discontinuity-Based. In similarity-based approach, segmentation is done based on grouping of pixels based on some features. In discontinuity-based approach the partition is done based on some abrupt changes in gray level intensity of the image. a)Detection of Isolated Points b)Detection of Lines c)Edge Detection [3]. The agriculture sector can be considered as the backbone for any developing economy. To obtain the maximum yield from the crops, it is required that farmers should be provided with the best technologies and methodologies.

Coconut is a palm plantation vital for its various uses from its fruit to trunk. India is the third-largest producer of coconut and its by-products in the world [4]. The southern states of India contribute a majority of the production in the country. Any disease affecting the yield of the coconut plantation eventually affects the related industries and the livelihood of the families who depend on the coconut economy [5].

P. Balamurugan and R. Rajesh (2012) [6] deals with the classification of coconut tree leaves which are affected by one of the diseases named as 'leaf rot'. They used Neural Network Based System for the Classification of Leaf Rot Disease in Cocos Nucifera Tree Leaves. Abraham Chandy (2019) [7] proposed a precision agriculture technique to detect various pests in coconut trees with the help of NVIDIA Tegra System on Chip (SoC) along with a camera interfaced drone. The drone flies across the coconut farm and captures the images and processes the data using deep learning algorithm to identify the unhealthy and pest affected trees. The deep learning algorithm uses a set of sample pest database.

Dirami, Ahmed, et al (2013) [8] employed the Thresholding segmentation (THS), techniques to segment the images before going for the classification process. Alshawwa et.al., (2019) [9] proposed the expert System which was produced to help farmers in diagnosing many of the coconut diseases such as: Bud Rot, Leaf Rot, Stem Bleeding, Tanjore wilt and Root (wilt). In this paper, section 1 discusses about the introduction of the proposed work. The major diseases and pests which are affecting coconut tree are discussed in section 3. Section 4 elaborates the implementation

of YOLO v8 for segmentation of coconut tree images. The results and discussion of the proposed work is discussed in section 5. Section 6 gives the conclusion of the proposed work.

2. MAJOR DISEASES AFFECTING COCONUT TREES

a) Ganoderma – basal stem rot (BSR)

Basal stem rot (BSR) caused by the species of Ganoderma is one of the most devastating diseases of numerous perennial, coniferous and palmaceous hosts. The disease is also referred to as Thanjavur wilt, bole rot, Ganoderma disease and Anabe.

Fig.1. Ganoderma – basal stem rot

Fig.2. Root Wilt Disease

b) Root Wilt Disease (RWD)

Root (wilt) disease (RWD) caused by phytoplasma is one of the most devastating diseases of coconut palms. The major symptoms of the disease in leaves are wilting and drooping and flaccidity; ribbing, paling/yellowing and necrosis of leaflets are typical symptoms of foliar diseases.

c) Bud rot

Bud rot is a fatal disease of coconut palm, characterized by the rotting of the terminal bud and surrounding tissues. Even though it affects the palms of all ages, young palms in low lying and moist situations are more susceptible to the disease. Fungus perpetuates on the host debris, in crevices and natural openings of the dead tissue.

Fig.3. Bud rot

Fig.4. Leaf Blight

d) Leaf Blight

Bacterial leaf blight is a serious disease of coconuts during wet seasons. The drying up of the leaves from the tip downwards, the progress of infection being from the older leaves to the younger. The worst affected palms present the appearance of severe drought-affected trees.

e) Stem bleeding disease

A reddish-brown liquid oozes from cracks and holes in the stem. It seeps out and runs down the stem, turning black and staining the stem as it dries. The disease is caused by *Chalara paradoxa*, a mainly soil borne plant-pathogenic fungus that infects wounds and openings in the coconut stem.

Fig.5. Stem bleeding disease

Fig.6. Leaf rot

f) Leaf rot

The first symptom is the appearance of water-soaked brown lesions in the spear leaves of root-wilt affected palms. Gradually these spots enlarge and coalesce resulting in extensive rotting.

3. PESTS AFFECTING COCONUT TREES**a) Rhinoceros beetle**

Pest population occurs round the year but population maximum during June – September coinciding with the onset of monsoon

b) Red palm weevil

It is the most destructive pest of young coconut palms. Unlike the Rhinoceros beetle, the adult weevil is incapable of causing any direct damage to the tree; on the other hand, the early stages of the weevil are passed on the palm and the damage caused to the tree by the weevil larvae is often fatal.

Fig.7. Rhinoceros beetle

Fig.8. Red palm weevil

c) Black-headed caterpillar

The leaf eating black headed caterpillar, *Opisina arenosella* is a serious pest of coconut palm causing significant yield loss in all the coconut growing tracts of India. It infests coconut of all age groups and is a prolific feeder of coconut leaves.

d) Coconut Eriophyid Mite and Termite

Termites are likely to cause damage to transplanted seedlings particularly in the earlier stage (wilting of seedlings).

Fig.9. Black-headed caterpillar

Fig.10, Coconut Eriophyid Mite and Termite

In this paper, required data set is collected to detect the symptoms of the coconut plant diseases and pest infections. To remove the unwanted noise present in the captured image, median filter is used. YOLO v8 technique is used to segment the infected region in the image.

4. SEGMENTATION USING YOLO v8

YOLO v8 algorithm (You Only Look Once version 8) is a state-of-the-art deep learning model designed for real-time object detection and segmentation tasks. While YOLO traditionally excels at detecting bounding boxes around objects, YOLO v8 algorithm introduces the capability of performing pixel-level segmentation. Segmentation is the process of partitioning an image into multiple segments or regions, which makes it more useful for detailed tasks like object delineation. With the ability to generate masks for each detected object, YOLOv8 combines both detection and segmentation tasks within a single, unified model, thus facilitating more accurate and granular recognition.

YOLO v8' architecture provides several advantages for segmentation tasks. The key benefit lies in its ability to process both detection and segmentation simultaneously, significantly improving the efficiency of the model. This is accomplished through a hybrid approach where the model not only predicts bounding boxes but also generates segmentation masks. With YOLO v8, object boundaries are delineated more precisely, making it ideal for tasks such as instance segmentation, where each object in a scene needs to be uniquely identified and segmented. YOLOv8's high-speed inference allows it to operate in real-time, making it suitable for applications in autonomous driving, robotics, and medical image analysis.

YOLOv8 performs segmentation by integrating a segmentation head with the standard detection architecture. This segmentation head produces pixel-level masks for each detected object in the image. The model uses a convolutional neural network (CNN) backbone, typically a variant of Efficient Net or CSPDarkNet, to extract high-level features from the input image. These features are then passed through the segmentation head, which utilizes specialized layers like the DeepLabV3+ module to generate the final segmentation map. This allows YOLOv8 to output both the bounding boxes and the detailed masks of each object, offering more precise segmentation results compared to traditional detection models.

The ability to perform segmentation with YOLO v8 opens up numerous applications across various industries. In the field of autonomous driving, YOLO v8 can be used for semantic segmentation, identifying road lanes, vehicles, pedestrians, and other obstacles. In medical imaging, it can assist in segmenting organs, tumors, or other structures in radiological scans. Furthermore, in agriculture, YOLO v8 can help segment crops and detect diseases, enabling precision farming. The versatility of YOLO v8 for segmentation ensures that it can be applied in numerous domains where pixel-perfect detection of objects is crucial, and it continues to be refined for even better accuracy and performance in future iterations.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sample images shown in Figs 11(a), 12(a), 13(a) and 14(a) namely leaf blight, stem bleeding and healthy images are given as input to wiener filter. The pre processed outputs are presented in Figs. 11(b),12(b),13(b) and 14(b). The pre processed outputs are given as input to the segmentation like Yolo v8 algorithm. The segmentation results of the image processing algorithm are shown in Fig.11(c,d), 12 (c,d), 13(c,d) and 14(c,d). The results indicate that the Yolo v8 algorithm are properly segmented. . For example, stem bled regions and sections with holes are properly segmented. 400 images were used for classification of four coconut plant diseases namely Leaf blight, Stem bleeding, Root wilt disease and Bud rot. Table 1 gives the accuracy of proposed classification method

Table 1. Classification Accuracy

S.No	Disease	Samples taken	YOLO v8 Rightly detected
1	Leaf blight	100	95
2	Stem bleeding	100	96
3	Root Wilt Disease	100	96
4	Bud rot	100	96
	Total	400	383

Fig.11(a) Sample Image 1 (Leaf Blight)

Fig.11(b) Pre processed output

Fig.11(c) Segmented output using YOLOv8

Fig.12 (a) Sample Image 2 (Leaf Blight)

Fig.12(b) Pre processed output

Fig.12(c) Segmented output using YOLOv8

Fig.13(a) Sample Image 3 (Stem Bleeding)

Fig.13(b) Pre processed output

Fig.13(c) Segmented output using YOLOv8

Fig.14(a) Sample Image 4 (Healthy image)

Fig.14(b) Pre processed output

Fig.14(c) Segmented output using YOLOv8

6 CONCLUSION

In this paper, coconut tree diseases and pests affecting coconut trees were discussed. The coconut tree data set were collected, pre processed and segmented. Pre processing part has been carried by implementing wiener filter and segmentation part has been carried out by YOLO v8, "You Only Look Once version 8," Based on the experimental results, the efficiency of the proposed system can be mightily seen as accuracy shoots up to 95.75 %.

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